

Jamu Potential as Tourism Attraction of Sukoharjo, Central Java – A Review

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Abstract:

Jamu, a traditional Indonesian herbal beverage, has long been recognized for its health benefits and cultural significance. This study explores the potential of jamu as both a health product and a tourism attraction in Sukoharjo, Central Java. The rising awareness of health, particularly post-pandemic, has led to an increasing demand for jamu, especially among younger generations seeking healthier lifestyle alternatives. This trend presents an opportunity to integrate jamu into tourism, providing visitors with an immersive experience of traditional jamu production while promoting its health benefits. The study highlights the importance of community involvement, product innovation, and infrastructure development in positioning Sukoharjo as the “City of Jamu”. The findings suggest that Sukoharjo’s branding as a jamu tourism destination has the potential to boost the local economy, promote cultural heritage, and create sustainable livelihoods for the community. However, challenges such as marketing strategies and infrastructure development need to be addressed for this potential to be fully realized. This research advocates for a holistic approach to jamu tourism development, combining cultural heritage with modern tourism practices to establish Sukoharjo as a leading destination for jamu enthusiasts globally.

Keywords: *Jamu, Sukoharjo, Tourism attraction.*

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Introduction

Jamu has diverse meanings, derived from the combination of 'Jawa' and '*ngramu*', referring to herbal concoctions made by the Javanese, or from the Old Javanese word '*djampi*', meaning a method of healing with herbal remedies. Historical evidence shows that '*jamu*' dates back to the Mataram Kingdom era, as seen in illustrations of its preparation in archaeological sites like Liyangan, temple reliefs, and the Madhwapura inscription, which mentions jamu practitioners as '*Acaraki*'. During the colonial period, jamu gained scientific recognition, particularly when Jacobus Bontius used it to treat VOC Governor-General Jan Pieterszoon Coen in the 17th century. Today, jamu continues to evolve with various variants, with jamu gendong, originating from Nguter, Sukoharjo, Central Java, remaining the most popular (Kemenparekraf, 2024).

Jamu, a traditional Indonesian herbal beverage, has been recognized by UNESCO as an Intangible Cultural Heritage, highlighting its cultural significance. This recognition, granted on December 6, 2023, positions jamu as the 13th Indonesian cultural heritage to receive this honor (UNESCO, 2024). UNESCO values jamu as a cultural expression that fosters a connection between humans and nature, supporting Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially Good Health and Well-being (SDG 3), Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8), Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12), Life on Land (SDG 15) (UN, 2024).

Sukoharjo Regency holds a strategic position in Central Java, directly bordering Surakarta City and being part of the SUBOSUKAWONOSRATEN strategic area. It is surrounded by six regencies/cities: Surakarta, Karanganyar, Boyolali, Klaten, Gunung Kidul, and Wonogiri. Key districts such as Nguter, Sukoharjo, and Grogol are traversed by inter-provincial routes, making Sukoharjo a promising area for development and the growth of strategic sectors (Rizqita, 2021).

The many studies related to jamu in Sukoharjo reflect the great potential but can also cause confusion because the focus and findings of each study can be different. The potential of herbal medicine in Sukoharjo is very large, both as a health product and a tourist attraction. With increasing public awareness of the importance of health post-pandemic, the consumption of herbal products, including herbal medicine, is increasingly in demand, especially among young people who are looking for healthy alternatives with practical packaging. Villages such as Kenep have the potential to become herbal medicine-based tourist destinations, where visitors can learn directly about the making and benefits of herbal medicine. In addition, branding Sukoharjo as a "Jamu City" can attract national tourists and introduce herbal medicine as part of local culture. With community empowerment and innovative products, herbal medicine can become an important pillar in the local economy and tourism sector of Sukoharjo (Astuti et al., 2022; Marimin & Sugiman, 2016; Suryaningrum et al., 2024; Wahyudi et al., 2019).

This study demonstrates that jamu holds significant potential as both a health product and a tourism attraction in Sukoharjo. With the growing awareness of health, particularly in the post-pandemic era, jamu has gained popularity not only in traditional markets but also among younger generations. This trend presents a promising opportunity for Kenep Village to develop a tourism village centered around jamu, where visitors can learn about the traditional production process and experience its health benefits firsthand.

Kenep Village offers a unique opportunity to establish a distinctive tourism destination focused on jamu. In addition to introducing traditional jamu production, the village could provide visitors with immersive experiences that showcase the health benefits of jamu. By involving the local community in the creation and marketing of jamu-based products, Sukoharjo can stimulate the local economy and create sustainable livelihoods for its residents.

Sukoharjo's initiative to position itself as the "City of Jamu" holds great potential for enhancing its reputation as a national destination for jamu tourism. However, to fully realize this potential, efforts must be directed toward strong branding, consistent marketing strategies, and infrastructure development. The improvement of facilities and amenities will be crucial in supporting the growth of jamu-based tourism.

Furthermore, active community involvement in the development and promotion of jamu products is essential to creating a supportive ecosystem for the sustainability of this industry. Entrepreneurial education and training in jamu production will help local communities create innovative and high-quality products that meet market demands. This approach will not only contribute to the growth of jamu tourism but also improve the overall welfare of the local population.

Although challenges remain, such as the need for more effective marketing strategies and infrastructure development, the growing demand for herbal products and the promotion of Sukoharjo's cultural heritage present valuable opportunities for economic growth and tourism development. With an integrated approach, Sukoharjo has the potential to become a global icon for jamu tourism.

Research Method

The literature review method in qualitative research is used to collect, analyze, and synthesize relevant literature sources to provide an in-depth understanding of the topic being studied. The steps include identifying sources, selecting and analyzing, synthesizing findings, and drawing conclusions to identify patterns, trends, and gaps in existing research. This method is very useful for building theories or conceptual models and identifying areas of research that need further exploration.

This study was conducted using a structured article review approach following the 2020 PRISMA Statement (Page et al., 2021). The process began with selecting the topic of interest, followed by the preparation of key words, inclusion, exclusion criteria. The chosen keywords for the literature search were: “Jamu”, “Tourism Attraction”, and “Sukoharjo,” which were combined using the “AND” operator. A search in the Google Scholar database yielded 130 articles. Articles published within the last ten years (2015–2024) were then screened for duplicates, leaving 124 articles. These were assessed based on their titles, abstracts, and keywords, resulting in 35 irrelevant articles. This left 89 articles to be further examined based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Of these, 81 articles were excluded, and 8 articles remained to be assessed for eligibility. An article was excluded. 7 articles met the criteria and were included in the review. Table 1 outlines the inclusion and exclusion criteria, while Figure 1 illustrates the literature selection process, and the number of articles identified at each step.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Original article	Review article
Articles within the topic of jamu as a tourism attraction	Articles that are out the topic of jamu as tourism attraction
Article indexed by Google Scholar	Article is not index by Google Scholar
English or Indonesian language	Non-English or Indonesian language
Article published 2015 - 2024	Article published before 2015 or after 2024

Figure 1. Literature selection process

Results and Discussion

This study highlights the significant potential of jamu in Sukoharjo, both as a health product and a tourist attraction. The increasing public awareness of the importance of health, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, has led to a growing demand for herbal products, including jamu. This opens opportunities for businesses and jamu producers to develop products that are not only beneficial but also appealing to younger consumers, including students, who are becoming more health-conscious and interested in natural lifestyles (Suryaningrum et al., 2024).

Among the younger generation, particularly students, there is a preference for jamu products that are easily accessible, enjoyable to consume, and have a pleasant taste. This creates opportunities for producers to innovate in packaging, flavor, and presentation, such as offering ready-to-drink jamu or bottled products. Such innovations can increase the appeal of jamu to a wider market, including those who may have previously been less interested in traditional herbal products.

Kenep Village in Sukoharjo has significant potential to be developed into a jamu-based tourism village. The village can offer tourists hands-on experience in the traditional preparation of jamu, its health benefits, and introduce various types of jamu native to the area. Visitors could be engaged in learning the process of making jamu from local natural ingredients, enriching their travel experience and making Kenep a unique and attractive tourist destination (Marimin & Sugiman, 2016).

The development of a jamu tourism village also provides opportunities for local communities to be directly involved in tourism and entrepreneurship. Through training and mentoring, local residents can be empowered to create and market their own jamu products. This development will not only enhance the local economy but also create sustainable

livelihoods for the community. Active involvement from the local population in the jamu industry will strengthen the identity of the village and foster a greater sense of ownership over the success of the tourism village (Marimin & Sugiman, 2016).

Wahyudi et al. (2019) concluded that Sukoharjo's effort to brand itself as the "City of Jamu" has promising prospects. Although this branding is still in its early stages, the study indicates that positioning Sukoharjo as a national jamu tourism destination could increase interest among domestic and international tourists. To achieve this, an effective marketing strategy is essential to introduce Sukoharjo as a hub for high-quality jamu production. With a consistent approach, Sukoharjo's reputation as a jamu tourism destination can grow, attracting more visitors and boosting economic activities in the region. Furthermore, the success of the "City of Jamu" branding will depend heavily on the development of supporting infrastructure, such as transportation access, accommodations, and tourist facilities integrated with the jamu theme. Improving these facilities can support the growth of tourism and foster the development of new businesses in the tourism and creative economy sectors. Effective marketing and adequate infrastructure will strengthen Sukoharjo's appeal as a top jamu tourism destination.

In addition to the products themselves, the success of this development relies on comprehensive destination management. Therefore, collaboration between local government, private sectors, and the community is essential to create a high-quality and well-rounded tourism experience. This includes educational activities that involve tourists in the jamu-making process and providing detailed information about the health benefits of jamu. This enriched experience will add value to the jamu tourism destination and positively impact on the tourism industry in Sukoharjo.

The study on the "Kafe Jamu" in Nguter District, Sukoharjo Regency provides insightful findings that can significantly enhance the café's marketing and customer satisfaction strategies. By identifying the characteristics of the consumer decision-making process and analyzing customer satisfaction levels, the research offers a clear picture of where Kafe Jamu stands in terms of meeting customer expectations and what areas require improvement.

One of the key strengths of the study is its use of measurable metrics, such as the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA), which allow businesses to objectively assess customer satisfaction. The CSI value of 78.86% suggests that the majority of customers are satisfied with the quality of products and services offered by Kafe Jamu. This finding is encouraging, but it also implies that there is room for improvement. The use of the IPA matrix further helps to pinpoint specific attributes that Kafe Jamu should focus on to boost customer satisfaction (Astuti et al., 2022).

The study highlights the attributes that are performing well and should be maintained, such as the taste of the products, cleanliness, availability of parking and toilets, and reasonable pricing. These are aspects that contribute positively to the overall customer experience and should continue to be prioritized. On the other hand, the analysis identifies attributes that need attention, such as advertising and promotion, signage, service quality, and speed of service. These are crucial aspects of the marketing mix that can significantly impact customer perceptions and purchase decisions.

However, there are several limitations to the study that should be addressed in future research. First, the analysis of the marketing mix itself lacks depth. While the study identifies areas of strength and weakness, it does not provide a comprehensive exploration of how these elements fit into a broader marketing strategy. A more detailed examination of each component of the marketing mix (product, price, place, and promotion) and how they relate to customer preferences would provide a more holistic understanding of Kafe Jamu's marketing effectiveness.

Moreover, the study does not compare Kafe Jamu's marketing mix with that of its competitors in the local market. A comparative analysis would allow Kafe Jamu to better understand where it stands relative to other businesses and identify unique selling propositions that could set it apart. By evaluating the performance of similar establishments, Kafe Jamu can make more informed decisions regarding its marketing strategies. The study lacks consumer demographic data, which could provide valuable insights into the specific needs and preferences of different customer segments. Understanding the demographics (such as age, income, occupation, and lifestyle) would enable Kafe Jamu to tailor its marketing efforts more effectively and create personalized offerings that resonate with its target audience.

The development and advancement of tourist attractions require strategic planning and effective marketing to ensure they reach a wider audience. As tourism continues to grow, detailed and easily accessible information about destinations becomes essential for attracting prospective tourists. When tourists are well-informed about the attractions that meet their needs and preferences, they are more likely to choose those destinations. Therefore, strategic initiatives, such as the bundling strategy, can significantly impact the success and growth of these attractions.

A bundling strategy is a popular marketing approach where two or more related products or services are sold together at a price lower than their individual cost. In the context of tourism, this strategy can be highly effective in attracting visitors by offering them a more economical and attractive package. By grouping different types of attractions or activities, such as nature tourism, water tourism, museum visits, cultural heritage sites, sports events, shopping

experiences, religious landmarks, and educational tours, the bundling strategy encourages tourists to experience a variety of attractions in one trip. This approach not only boosts the number of tourists but also enhances the overall experience of visitors, as they can enjoy multiple experiences at a discounted price.

In regions like the Ex-Surakarta Residency, which boasts diverse tourist offerings, bundling strategies can be customized to cater to different tourist interests. For instance, a tourist package could combine a visit to a natural reserve, a local cultural museum, and a religious site. These types of bundles make it easier for tourists to plan their trips by offering all-inclusive experiences, which can be particularly appealing to both local and international tourists. This could also enhance the visibility of lesser-known attractions by including them in popular packages, leading to an overall increase in tourism traffic (Yuliari & Riyadi, 2019).

The key to successful bundling lies in its ability to attract a diverse range of tourists. By offering something for everyone, whether it's nature lovers, history enthusiasts, or shoppers, bundles can address the varying interests and needs of different traveler segments. Moreover, this strategy can improve the competitiveness of local destinations by offering unique combinations that stand out in the marketplace.

However, the success of this strategy requires careful planning and collaboration between tourism providers. It is essential to ensure that all components of the bundle are well-coordinated, that the pricing is attractive, and that the marketing is clear and effective. Local stakeholders, including hotels, transport services, guides, and other businesses, should be engaged to create a seamless experience for tourists.

In addition, innovation in planning is crucial to keep the offerings fresh and exciting. The tourism industry is dynamic, and visitor preferences can change over time. Thus, continuously updating and enhancing the bundles, based on tourist feedback and emerging trends, will help keep the destinations relevant and appealing (Wahyudi et al., 2019).

Ultimately, the bundling strategy is an effective tool for increasing the attractiveness and competitiveness of regional tourist attractions. As more tourists visit, the destinations will evolve and improve, leading to the overall growth and sustainability of tourism in the area. By making it easier and more affordable for tourists to explore various attractions, bundling can play a pivotal role in enhancing the local economy and fostering long-term tourism development.

Susanti et al., (2023) on the role of digital media in tourism branding in Sukoharjo Regency provides valuable insights into how digital-based branding strategies can play a significant role in the development of the tourism sector, particularly in rural tourism villages. Sukoharjo, with its vast potential for tourism development, demonstrates that digital technology is a crucial strategy in promoting tourist destinations. The success of tourism promotion through digital media requires effective collaboration between stakeholders, including village governments, local communities, and other tourism-related businesses.

The use of digital media for tourism branding offers several advantages, one of the most significant being its broad reach. Digital media allows tourism information to be disseminated quickly and efficiently, making it easier to reach a larger audience, both local and international. Digital platforms enable the presentation of content in various forms, such as text, images, and videos, which can engage a wider range of tourists. Therefore, it is essential for tourism village managers in Sukoharjo to take full advantage of various digital platforms, such as social media, websites, and apps, to effectively showcase their tourism potential.

However, the success of tourism promotion through digital media is not only reliant on the technology itself but also on the effective collaboration between various stakeholders. Local governments, communities, and tourism businesses must work together to create engaging and relevant promotional content that resonates with their target audience. Additionally, the ability to manage digital technologies is also a critical factor, as engaging content requires a good understanding of how to effectively use digital platforms.

The necessary steps for implementing a digital-based promotion strategy include preparing digital promotional strategies, creating and managing content in the form of text, images, and videos, and continually evaluating the effectiveness of the strategies in place. It is vital to have a continuous evaluation process to assess whether the strategy is effectively attracting tourists and increasing visits to the tourism village. This evaluation could be based on social media interactions, website traffic, or direct feedback from tourists who visit the destinations.

Furthermore, the development of digital-based tourist villages requires increased human resource capabilities. Community members and tourism managers must be trained and supported in digital media management, content creation, and the use of relevant technology. Without this capacity-building, the enormous potential of tourist villages may remain untapped. Strengthening human resources also plays a key role in ensuring the long-term sustainability of digital tourism management, so that tourism can be continuously developed and maintained.

Overall, this study demonstrates that to maximize the potential of tourism, an integrated and sustainable approach is required when using digital media for branding and promotion. This involves collaboration between local governments, communities, and the private sector to effectively use technology to attract more tourists and enhance the tourism sector in the region. If this strategy is implemented successfully, digital tourism promotion in Sukoharjo could serve as a model that can be replicated in other regions to promote sustainable and digital-based tourism development on a broader scale.

Conclusion

Sukoharjo has significant potential to be developed into a jamu-based tourism village, offering tourists the opportunity to learn about traditional jamu preparation and its health benefits. This development could empower local communities by involving them in the production and marketing of jamu products, enhancing the local economy and creating sustainable livelihoods. Sukoharjo's branding efforts as the "City of Jamu" hold promise, and with effective marketing strategies and infrastructure improvements, the region can attract both domestic and international tourists. A collaborative approach among local government, businesses, and communities, alongside innovations like digital media promotion, will be key to establishing Sukoharjo as a leading jamu tourism destination, fostering long-term growth and sustainability.

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